

“KVADRAT TENGLAMALAR” BOBINI O’QITISHDA INTERFAOL TA’LIM USULLARIDAN FOYDALANISH

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O’quv jarayonida samaradorlikka erishish uchun zamonaviy ilg’or pedagogik texnologiyalar, noan’anaviy dars usullari va o’zaro faol o’quv jarayonini tadbiiq qilish lozim. O’zaro faol usullarni o’quv jarayoniga qo’llash uchun esa o’tiladigan mavzuni talabalar, o’quvchilar o’zlari mustaqil tayyorlab kelishlari talab etiladi. Jarayonning samaradorligini oshirish maqsadida innovatsion usullarini qo’llashda endi biz pedagoglar O’quvchlarni o’qitmaymiz, balki kitobni o’qishga o’rgatamiz shiorini amalga oshiramiz. Buning sababi shundaki, agarda talaba va o’quvchilar darsga tayyor holda kelmasalar, hech qanaqa faol usuldan samarali foydalanib bo’lmaydi. Natijada o’qituvchi yana o’z-o’zidan an’an’anaviy shaklda dars o’tishiga tog’ri keladi.

Kvadrat tenglama

Ushbu $ax^2 + bx + c = 0, (a \neq 0)$ (1)

Ko’rinishdagi tenglamaga kvadrat tenglama deyiladi, bu yerda a, b, c o’zgarmas koeffitsientlar. Kvadrat tenglamani ildizlarini topish uchun (1) tenglikni $4a$ ga ko’paytiramiz:

$$4a^2 x^2 + 4abx + 4ac = 0, \quad (2ax)^2 + 2(2ax)b + b^2 - b^2 + 4ac$$

$$(2ax + b)^2 = b^2 - 4ac$$

$$2ax + b = \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}$$

yoki $x_{1;2} = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$ (2)

(2) formula bilan topilgan x_1 va x_2 (1) tenglamaning ildizidir.

Misol. $3x^2 - 5x - 2 = 0$ kvadrat tenglamani yeching.

Yechish. $a = 3, b = -5, c = -2$ bo’lganida (2) formulaga asosan.

$$x_{1;2} = \frac{5 \pm \sqrt{5^2 - 4 \cdot 3 \cdot (-2)}}{2 \cdot 3} = \frac{5 \pm 7}{6}, \quad x_1 = \frac{5+7}{6} = 2; \quad x_2 = \frac{5-7}{6} = -\frac{1}{3}$$

Agar $ax^2 + bx + c = 0$ kvadrat tenglamada $a = 1$ bo’lsa, tenglikni $a \neq 0$ ga bo’lsak, hosil bo’lgan kvadrat tenglamaga keltirilgan kvadrat tenglama deyiladi va

$$x^2 + px + q = 0 \quad (3)$$

Ko’rinishda yoziladi, bu yerda $p = \frac{b}{a}, q = \frac{c}{a}$ bo’lib, (2) formula quyidagi ko’rinishda bo’ladi.

$$x_{1;2} = \frac{-p \pm \sqrt{p^2 - 4q}}{2} \quad (4)$$

Agar (1) kvadrat tenglamaning b va c koeffitsientlaridan biri yoki ikkalasi bir vaqtda nolga teng bo’lsa, hosil bo’lgan tenglamaga chala kvadrat tenglama deyiladi.

Chala kvadrat tenglamalar quyidagi ko’rinishlarga ega bo’ladi:

1). $ax^2 + c = 0, (a \neq 0, b = 0, c \neq 0)$

Agar a va c ning ishoralari qarama – qarshi bo'lsa, $x_{1;2} = \pm \sqrt{-\frac{c}{a}}$ ikkita haqiqiy ildizga va bir

xil ishorali bo'lsa, $x_{1;2} = \pm i \sqrt{-\frac{c}{a}}$ mavhum ildizlarga ega bo'lamiz.

2). $ax^2 + bx = 0$, ($a \neq 0, b \neq 0, c = 0$) bo'lsa,

$$x(ax + b) = 0, \quad x_1 = 0, \quad x_2 = -\frac{b}{a} \text{ bo'ladi.}$$

3). $ax^2 = 0$, ($a \neq 0, b = c = 0$) bo'lsa, $x_1 = x_2 = 0$ bo'ladi.

Misollar. Quyidagi chala kvadrat tenglamalarni yeching:

a). $9x^2 - 49 = 0$ b). $3x^2 + 7x = 0$ c). $8x^2 = 0$

Yechish: Ravshanki, berilgan kvadrat tenglamalar yuqorida ko'rilgan kvadrat tenglamalarning 1), 2), 3) ko'rinishiga mos keladi

a). $9x^2 - 49 = 0$ b). $x(3x + 7) = 0$
 $x^2 = \frac{49}{9}$, $x_{1;2} = \pm \frac{7}{3}$ $x_1 = 0$, $x_2 = -\frac{7}{3}$ c). $8x^2 = 0$
 $x_1 = x_2 = 0$

(2) formulada ildiz ostidagi $b^2 - 4ac$ ifodaga kvadrat tenglamaning diskreminanti deyiladi va $D = b^2 - 4ac$ ko'rinishda belgilanadi.

Kvadrat tenglamani yechmasdan uni ildizlari qanday son bo'lishini aniqlashga, kvadrat tenglamani tekshirish deyiladi.

Kvadrat tenglamani tekshirganda quyidagi uch xol qaraladi:

1. $D > 0$, bunda kvadrat tenglamaning iddizlari haqiqiy va har xil

bo'lib, $x_1 = \frac{-b + \sqrt{D}}{2a}$, $x_2 = \frac{-b - \sqrt{D}}{2a}$ bo'ladi.

2. $D = 0$ bo'lsa, kvadrat tenglama ikkita bir xil haqiqiy ildizga ega bo'ladi, ya'ni

$$x_1 = x_2 = -\frac{b}{2a}$$

3. $D < 0$ bo'lsa, kvadrat tenglama ikkita qo'shma kompleks ildizga ega

bo'ladi: $x_1 = \frac{-b + i\sqrt{-D}}{2a}$; $x_2 = \frac{-b - i\sqrt{-D}}{2a}$

Insoniyat kamoloti hayotning rivoji texnika va texnologiyalarning takomillashib borish asosida fanlar o'qitilishiga bo'lgan talablarini hisobga olgan holda maktab matematika kursini ularning zamonaviy rivoji bilan uyg'unlashtirish maktabda o'quvchilarga matematikani o'qitishdan ko'zda tutilgan asosiy maqsadlardan biridir. Matematika fani o'quvchilarni iroda, diqqatni to'plab olishni; qobiliyat va faollikni, tasavvurining rivojlangan bo'lishini talab eta borib, mustaqil, ma'suliyatli, mehnatsevar, intizomli va mantiqiy fikrlash hamda o'zining qarash va e'tiqodlarini dalillar asosida himoya qila olish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishni talab qiladi. Hozirgi zamon darsiga qo'yiladigan eng muhim talablardan biri har bir darsda tanlanadigan mavzuning ilmiy asoslangan bo'lishidir, ya'ni darsdan ko'zlangan maqsad hamda o'quvchilar imkoniyatini hisobga olgan holda mavzu xajmini belgilash uning murakkabligini aniqlash, avvalgi o'rganilgan mavzu bilan bog'lash, o'quvchilarga beriladigan topshiriq va mustaqil ishlarning ketma-ketligini aniqlash, darsda kerak bo'ladigan jihozlarni belgilash va qo'shimcha ko'rgazmali qurollar bilan boyitish, qo'shimcha axborot texnologiyalardan

foydalangan holda muammoli vaziyatni yaratishdir. Dars davomida o'qituvchi o'quvchilarning jismoniy holatini, ijodkorligini, tez fikrlashlarini hisobga olishi kerak.

References:

1. Davronovich, Aroyev Dilshod, and Juraev Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "IMPORTANT ADVANTAGES OF ORGANIZING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN A DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY ENVIRONMENT." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 11.2 (2023): 149-154.
2. Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon, and Aroyev Dilshod Davronovich. "INTERDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION IS AN IMPORTANT PART OF DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS." *Open Access Repository* 9.1 (2023): 93-101.
3. Zhumakulov, H. K. "CONDITIONS FOR THE CONVERGENCE OF BRANCHING PROCESSES WITH IMMIGRATION STARTING FROM A LARGE NUMBER OF PARTICLES." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.12 (2022): 309-313.
4. Эсонов, Минаввар Мукимжанович. "Методические приёмы творческого подхода в обучении теории изображений." *Вестник КРАУНЦ. Физико-математические науки* 7.2 (2013): 78-83.
5. Mukimzhonovich, Esonov Munavarzhon. "FEATURES OF GEOMETRIC PROBLEMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SELF-AWARENESS AND LOGICAL THINKING." *Open Access Repository* 8.12 (2022): 185-190.
6. Sharipovich, Akhmadaliyev Shakhobidin. "THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL PRINCIPLES OF CREATING LEARNING SYSTEMS ON THE MOODLE LMS PLATFORM." *Conferencea* (2023): 1-6.
7. Jumaqozievich, Yuldashev Utkir. "Systematic approach in education as a methodological problem." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429 11.09 (2022): 269-271.
8. qizi Yakubjonova, Maftunaxon Islomjon. "KINO TA'LIMI VA INTERNET-TELEVIDENIESINING ASOSIY FUNKSIYALARI." *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES*. Vol. 1. No. 2. 2022.
9. Khasanov, A. R. "LEARNING IS A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH AS A CONTENT UPDATE STEP." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.12 (2022): 217-223.
10. Mansurjonovich, J. M., and Y. S. Sattorovich. "MAXSUS IZLAMALARDAN FOYDALANISH TA'LIM JARAYONINI TASHKIL ETISHNING MUHIM AVTOZYATLARI." *Ochiq kirish ombori* 4.3 (2023): 126-133.
11. Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon, and Yuldashev Sherzod Sattorovich. "IMPORTANT ADVANTAGES OF ORGANIZING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS USING SPECIAL APPLICATIONS." *Open Access Repository* 4.3 (2023): 126-133.
12. Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon, and Rakhimov Jorabek Rashidjan o'g'li. "DESIGNING THE STRATEGY OF STUDENT INDIVIDUALITY IN INDEPENDENT RESEARCH ACTIVITY." *Open Access Repository* 9.4 (2023): 433-437.

13. Jo'Rayev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "KIBER PEDAGOGIKA–XXI ASRDA RAQAMLI TA'LIM MUHITI PEDAGOGIKASI." Academic research in educational sciences 4.KSPI Conference 1 (2023): 103-110.
14. Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon, and Muzaffar Mansurovich Botirov. "Characteristics Of Teaching Programming Based On Different Principles." Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology 17 (2023): 85-90.
15. Mansurjonovich, J. M. "Methodological foundations for improving the content of training future ict teachers in the conditions of digital transformation of education." Актуальные вопросы современной науки и образования 9 (2022).
16. Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "Pedagogical conditions for the development of vocational education through interdisciplinary integration into the vocational education system." НАУКА, ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ, ОБЩЕСТВО: АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ, ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ. 2021.
17. Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Professional Educational Institutions Theoretical and Practical Basis of Development of the Content of Pedagogical Activity of Teachers of" Information and Information Technologies"." Open Access Repository 9.12 (2022): 85-89.
18. Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "CURRENT STATUS OF THE SCIENCE OF INFORMATICS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION SYSTEM, EXISTING PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS, PRINCIPLES AND CONTENT OF THE SCIENCE ORGANIZATION." Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal 10.12 (2022): 327-331.
19. Xudayberdiyev, Zayniddin Yavkachevich, and Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich Juraev. "Theoretical analysis of the continuity model of computer science and information technology in the system of professional education." (2021).
20. Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Description of the Methodological Basis for Ensuring Interdisciplinary Continuity of the Subject" Computer Science and Information TECHNOLOGY" in Vocational Education." JournalNX 7.10: 223-225